

Motorway Tunnels Resilience Through Automated Deformation Monitoring

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ABSTRACT

In years where most of the road infrastructures are severely ageing worldwide, but still enormously contributing to transportation smoothness (people, cargo, etc.), careful monitoring attention is needed in mind of climate/weather change (extreme events, natural/man-made disasters, material aging, etc.) and capacity needs increase (increased flows for users). These factors are contributing to the overall network resilience as an important contributor to their long-term sustainability. Sustainability of the road network directly affects economical, social, and environmental aspects that indicate the overall value of their resilience and the urgent needs for adaptations, monitoring, risk management/analysis and forecasting, but also effective vulnerability modelling and assessment approaches. In the later dimension, this publication presents recent research results on a 3D modelling approach and methodology for measuring deformations in highway tunnels using 3D laser imaging sensors and consolidating the results in an approach to early detect deformations and structural deteriorations over time. The system is able to perform analysis of a 3D model of the infrastructure at millimeter level and provide comparisons with existing (previous) models to detect abnormalities in the 3D shape of the tunnel (intrados) as results of partial deformations. An early indication of any infrastructure deterioration is pinpointed and georeferenced for immediate uptake in the maintenance planning of highway safety teams and maintenance personnel, including 3D geometrical information on the defect position. At a next stage, the system can be integrated on an autonomous navigating robotic system that is able to position the sensing device at particular inspection points of interest or the suitable points for a holistic infrastructure measurement/modelling. This research presents recent research results of INLECOM INNOVATION in the running, European Commission (EC) co-funded, research project, PILOTING (<https://piloting-project.eu/>) currently during its 2nd year of execution over robotic inspection for the oil & gas and transport (viaducts and tunnels) infrastructures.

1. INTRODUCTION AND SUMMARY

Appropriate monitoring of the global transport infrastructure and in particular road network, is nowadays essential to support the world's wealth, economic growth, access to services, and social cohesion in the EU, especially as parts of CEF/TEN-T corridors. Poorly maintained roads constrain mobility, significantly increase accidents and fatality rates (both for workers and users) and aggravate isolation, poverty, and poor health in rural communities. Road transport as a foundation of economic activities, typically lies between 3% - 5% GDPs, that adding fuel and transport equipment can rise to 20%. At the same time, following data from the International Transport Forum, considering OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) countries, road transport accounts for up to 83% of passenger travel. Roads are considered as key national assets underpinning national economic activities comprising millions of kilometers across the world. Road maintenance controls depreciation in value and directly affects road users both in terms of road service

quality and safety issues. Consequently, we need to consider the ageing infrastructure requiring improved maintenance levels to avoid traffic disruption. On top, the increase in traffic volumes further raises the need for efficient maintenance to maximize infrastructure capacities for passengers and freight [1]. There are several, however, ECs priorities, instruments and directives towards a safer road transport, reduction of accidents, congestions and costs transferred to users and operators (Towards an EU Road Safety Area: policy recommendations 2011-2030 [2]).

When focusing on tunnel constructions as parts of a highway 'system' (comprising of other modules also e.g., bridges, pavement, side-pavement, ventilation, drainage, etc.) their practical peculiarities need to be considered as well as related, particular challenges. However, despite some really high challenges in their appropriate inspection and maintenance approach and methodologies, consideration of their regular inspection and follow-up of potential damages stays essential and remains of high priority for transport authorities, inspection teams and highway operators. Inspection and maintenance activities inside tunnels include dangers much greater than working in open space as a result of their nature and reduced lighting, shaded areas, high humidity levels, dusty and slippery conditions, as well as physical dimension constraints such as narrow width and other obstacles [3]. Not to forget live traffic, such conditions require very timely and precise tunnel inspection at increased speed, lower cost, decreased personnel exposure, while providing high accuracy results being regularly updated and providing the chance to compare over damage escalation in time.

1.1. Tunnel Inspection Industrial Challenges and Existing Solutions

There are different tunnel types due to construction method (cut and cover, shield driven, bored, drill and blast etc) consisting of different final liner types. The project focuses on the structural inspection of tunnels rather the operational systems that exist in a modern road tunnel (ventilation, traffic management systems, power distribution, communication etc), as this is the most important for the safety of the users, the lifetime of the structure and the most difficult part to assess. Choosing the common cast in-place final liner type, several defects can occur on the liner which has to be detected and assessed for rehabilitation.

Maybe the most important and critical defect in a tunnel component is any change to its shape (including the lining and any components or structural attachments, barriers etc.), that will be referred hereof as deformation. Deformation in a civil structure can be defined as including any change in the geometrical shape of the structure other than those originally created for. In other words, any modification in the geometrical properties of the structure that could alter the original (and intended) operation. In particular, for tunnels, this could happen due to heavy loads surrounding the tunnel, concrete deterioration, re-enforcement failures (due to corrosion, reinforcement failure, yielding or excessive bending at cracks, debonding or other structural failures) and other reasons, that are in-turn linked to other events such as water penetration, leakages, delamination, spalling and other defects.

Maintaining the integrity of tunnels remains of high priority, especially in countries and road areas where the transport infrastructure itself shows increased deterioration signs. Therefore, precise systems are needed able to make repeatable measurements of the tunnel shape with increased accuracy and seriously respecting transport safety and precautions (workers' safety, timely inspections, high accuracy of measurements, etc.). Existing methodologies of tunnel (reinforced concrete, masonry, etc.) structural inspections are based on manual efforts to record defects that remain on tunnel surface (cracks, spalling, etc.), involving manual measurements and workers field exposure. Further, current measurement data collection and processing are not taking place in a structured monitoring

manner, thus difficult to repeat under the same conditions and not allowing the comparison with measurements over time to derive the escalation (or not) of structural damages/deformations over time. Capturing the structural deformation of a whole tunnel or a big section, in 3D is one of the primary interests during inspection activities as it proves the actual health of the tunnel, reinforcements, surroundings and links to maintenance activities. Today, this is performed only at local points via topography/geodetic and surveyor tools that only perform point-to-point measurements, making it impossible to reconstruct a whole tunnel in 3D and has limited repeatability. 3D laser scanning tools are also used but are: (a) limited to local inspections for reasons of extended worker field exposure, field positioning issues, inability of consecutive scanning and model combining; (b) provide limited accuracy as their resolution is reduced to minimize the worker field-exposure which results into lower quality measurements.

This developed inspection approach and methodology is directly targeting the markets of inspection and maintenance (roads and highways) and Non-destructive-testing (NDT) actors in transport (road safety market). In Europe, the road safety market projection CAGR for support and maintenance activities (2020-2024) is 11.2% (Markets & Markets), considered 1st in the professional services for road safety between consulting, integration, training, deployment, etc. (with a size growth reaching 1.5b€ by 2024). The potential end-users/clients range in the sectors of inspection and maintenance teams, civil inspection actors, transport/road owners/operators, and managers as well as public authorities that are all expected to directly benefit from the innovative solution.

1.2. Tunnel Description and Baselines

Own properties of tunnels include supporting its own weight, having several loads from the interface of lining and ground, exhibiting effects of hydrostatic pressure from water existing at the tunnel extrados, as well as experiencing thermal stresses and shrinkage, operating loads, and periodic loads (e.g. traffic, etc.). At the same time, a tunnel can operate perfectly and last for several years as long as the conditions allow. The scope of the usual construction method NATM (New Austrian Tunnelling Method), relies on the achievement of structural tensions' equilibrium during the construction time while the final internal liner (cast in place) is designed to undertake any further loads that can be exercised during the operation of the structure. In some cases due to ageing of the structure and/or the development of extra loads (and other reasons) can cause deformations and damages even with destructive consequences.

There are several components of a tunnel system that we need to clarify at this point, and they are all somehow interconnected to a possible deterioration of a tunnel, such as a deformation. The first part is the portals of the tunnel, as the actual extension of the tunnel located at both its two ends and extending for some meters serving safety, air ventilation and also aesthetic purposes. Ancillary structures usually include the ventilation stations that often support tunnels of great length and may also include shafts, parallel bores, evacuation galleries, etc. Such structures differ a lot in shape, size, and inspection requirements. The tunnel interior is the length of a tunnel cross-section [3]. The lined section of a tunnel is the section (partially or totally) supported by the internal lining (can be of brick, masonry/stone, sprayed concrete, cast-in-place/situ, or prefabricated). Two more important definitions include the tunnel intrados (surface of the lower part of the tunnel crown, invert, and internal surface of the walls) and extrados (the convex outer surface of the tunnel lining). It is the intrados that often shows the first indicators of defects, including possible cracks, or other deterioration signs, that can lead to more focused and monitored inspection activities.

1.3. Tunnel Deformation Inspection Requirements

Road tunnels are built to allow the passing of vehicles/traffic through areas that otherwise passing would be impossible. The ultimate requirement is to keep them in operational condition for the safety and comfort of users. Due to their ageing and harsh operational conditions, it is highly required to perform regular inspections on the surface and especially deformation (that is the scope of this work) that could affect their stability and structural health.

Current inspection approaches are based on topography or geodetic approaches that are cumbersome in terms of workers' safety, live traffic condition, precision and accuracy of measurements, large inspection time and the capability to register the measurements in a common coordinate system for revisiting and comparison in later times. It can be noted that there might be severe deformation ongoing that due to its slow escalation/progress in time, it needs periodical inspections. Following the bibliography, current methodologies include i) inspection, maintenance and monitoring of civil works to detect and identify causes and nature of the possible deteriorations, inspection data gathering and surveying approaches, ii) maintaining safety and operational equipment and structures and iii) actual maintenance works. At the same time, inspections are divided into i) periodic (annual, assessment, detailed), and ii) one-off (initial, due to an event, end of constructions, after large works, change of contractors, etc.) [4] [5].

The designed solution is aware of both current shortcomings, limitations, and obstacles that limit the efficiency of existing approaches taking advantage of autonomous, high precision and repeatability. This is here examined as part of the PILOTING, EC, research project.

1.4. The PILOTING Project Summary

The PILOTING project (PILOTs for robotic INSpection and maintenance Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and prototype applications) (GA number: 871542), focuses on new solutions that are being explored to develop low-cost yet large-scale systems that can assist with infrastructure maintenance. The EU-funded PILOTING project is proposing a robotic inspection solution. More specifically, it will develop an integrated platform demonstrating the application of robotics at scale in the domain of inspection and maintenance. The project will conduct three demonstration/validation piloting exercises in different sectors: oil and gas refineries, highway/rail bridges and road tunnels. The goal is to minimise the costs, risks, and disruptions associated with structural inspections and maintenance.

The project focuses on existing EU refineries and civil infrastructures (tunnels and bridges) that are ageing, and therefore gradually become deteriorated, especially taking into consideration the current and future economic situation in Europe where large investments in renewing infrastructures are not foreseen while there is a high need to increase the efficiency and quality of inspection and maintenance activities to keep the necessary safety levels in these ageing infrastructures. To overcome these challenges, PILOTING proposes the adaptation, integration, and demonstration of robotic solutions, in an integrated platform, which will be tested and evaluated in three large-scale pilots: refineries (Oil&Gas sector), bridges/viaducts and tunnels (Civil/Transport Infrastructure sector) with the involvement of all the actors that conform the full value chain. The developed platform will: demonstrate the application of robotics at scale in the domain of Inspection and Maintenance (I&M), reduce end-user commercial risks on the deployment of robotics in the sector, demonstrate capabilities and improve understanding of robotics uptake value, develop and support the related ecosystem around the piloting I&M operations, as well as, contribute to industrial

standards in robotics for I&M. To achieve the above, PILOTING will develop an advanced robotic-based platform that will be deployed in the three industrial scenarios and demonstrate the real value towards the inspection and maintenance community as well as its high level socio-economic impact when applied at scale.

Part of this solution is an autonomous, robotic vehicle supported by advanced laser sensing devices that will perform autonomous tunnel deformation inspection and monitoring. This work is coordinated by INLECOM Innovation (Greece) - responsible for the inspection and maintenance software platform design as well as responsible for the tunnel inspection.

PILOTING will establish large-scale pilots in real industrial environments to directly reply to main I&M challenges through the demonstration of increasing rate of inspection and maintenance tasks, improving coverage and performance, decreasing costs and time of operations, improving inspection quality and increasing safety of operators.

2. 3D TUNNEL DEFORMATION MONITORING

2.1. Laser scanning for tunnel deformation detection

The objective of this work was to create 3D models in the tunnel use cases through accurate 3D point clouds of it using laser scanning technologies. These 3D models will be used to perform tunnel structural deformation assessments with very high accuracy by comparing several scans in different time periods [6] [7]. During the final pilot demonstrations (expected during Q2-3 of 2021), a 3D laser scanner device will be carried (fully integrated) by a robotic vehicle, which will perform laser scanning automatically in predefined locations across the tunnel, as described in the robotic mission definition (and triggered by the road robotic vehicle). The generated models will be presented to the end-user through a web-based visualization portal to support damage escalation and deformation monitoring. For this purpose, test and training material was required to validate the feasibility and accuracy of the 3D reconstruction of the tunnel [8] [9] [10].

A first round and collection of the initial material took place in Metsovo tunnels (EGANTIA motorway) (drainage and main highway tunnel) in October 2020 with the participation of INLECOM Innovation (Greece) and support from Egnatia Motorway (Greece). For the test data collected, two sections of the Egnatia Motorway network were used: 1) Metsovo Tunnel (main TEN-T corridor) and 2) Drainage Tunnel (no traffic – only drainage purposes). For the first one, a large section of the Egnatia Motorway (Metsovo tunnel) was separated from traffic for several hours across three days of experiments. A hand-moveable tripod with the scanner fixed on it was used in both cases to simulate the actual (final) position of the scanner on the robotic vehicle, while several alternative positions (in terms of height and tunnel perpendicular axis) were tried to investigate advantages, disadvantages as well as possible limitations in installation and positioning. Several scans have been carried out, as presented in the figure below, with a view to reconstruct a specific part of the tunnel. Regarding the capturing conditions, no external lighting was used, and the scanning was performed without any artificial targets (as a first approach) with the aim to reconstruct and co-register the captured models automatically based on top geometry and information.

Figure 1 - Drainage Tunnel, laser scanner data set collection

Figure 2 - Metsovo tunnel 3D laser scanner data set collection

2.2. Technical Challenges

The technical challenges that were faced during these experiments included the following:

- 1) Live traffic: to overcome obstacles and live traffic (safety wise), it was decided to stop the traffic in one lane of the tunnel (left or right side) so the laser scanner could be positioned on the road pavement for precise and stable measurements (3D cloud point creation).
- 2) Co-registration of models: due to the homogeneous layout of tunnels (very similar visual representation even of different sections), manual co-registration of the models would prove extremely time consuming. As this is work in progress, the use of tags seems to be the optimal solution.
- 3) Lighting conditions: despite that lighting conditions vary strongly inside tunnels (esp. start and end points), the selection of the laser technology was beneficial as it was not affected by the differing lighting conditions of the tunnel.
- 4) Registration of coordinate system: to cope with the revisiting needs (scanning from exactly the same point), a common coordinate system would be needed. As this is also work in progress, the solution would rely on the usage of an autonomous

navigation and positioning robotic system/vehicle that has precise odometry information and can trigger the sensors at the appropriate (revisited points).

2.3. First Validation and Results at Egnatia Motorway (Greece) Tunnels

This initial data set has supported the researchers to familiarize with the actual data measurements to be performed and validated at the tunnel cases in Egnatia Motorway and pave the way for the automatic execution of the laser scanning measurements by an autonomous robotic vehicle. The collection of this first data set has also provided consecutive tunnel measurements, in exactly the same way that will be performed by the robotic system. Experimentation with this data set will further support the researchers to define a common measurement approach, accuracy and resolution as well as the proper approach for merging (co-registering) the different measured models (point clouds) in a single model of a particular section of the tunnel (of structural inspection importance and interest). In the following months, more data are planned to be collected, these being more precise on the actual inspection points in the tunnels (indicative positions).

This first validation of the approach took place from October 2020 to June 2021, with several visits to the site under investigation. For this, the above apparatus was used with the following inspection specifications:

- Point cloud number: 10.9M points
- Point distance mm/10m: 12.2 mm
- Point distance mm/2.5m: 3.1 mm
- Inspection time (per scan): 5.5 minutes
- Total inspection time (150m of tunnel): 2.5 hours
- Distance between consecutive scans: 30-50m

A first visual representation of the Metsovo tunnel can be found below using the specifications above.

Figure 3: Metsovo tunnel 3D reconstruction (external view)

Figure 4: Metsovo tunnel 3D reconstruction (internal view)

The analysis of the above measurements has led to the following conclusions. Most of them are under investigation and planned for the next round of the approach validation, planned in two stages, July-December 2021 and January-September 2022. Details follow in the conclusions chapter.

- 1) It is possible to make manual measurements over the created point-cloud (scans) however, an automated approach would be quicker and more detailed.
- 2) The presence of noise (passing cars, etc.) would matter only from the side of inspection importance (left of right), so the suitable side should be selected for closing traffic.
- 3) Noise points in the cloud could be deleted manually but with some good effort.
- 4) To facilitate co-registration of models and merging into one single model, common (visual) points have to be located (manually), which is also a time-consuming and prone to error task.
- 5) In order to enable common visiting points landmarks have to be used, which is rather cumbersome and prone to error as well.
- 6) Lighting conditions do not affect the scanned areas and inspection can be performed flawlessly and without any impact on accuracy.
- 7) Duration of each inspection, needs to be reduced but this would define the model resolution.
- 8) Scanner installation on truck could be investigated. Following the recent results, it should be ensured that truck is stable (Not shaking or moving) during the whole scan duration.

3. CONCLUSIONS, NEXT STEPS AND UPCOMING ROADMAP

3.1. Benefits of Autonomous Inspection in Tunnels

The benefits of autonomous inspection in tunnels is summarised below:

- 1) Reduction of noise, vibration and air-pollution (global CO₂) and improve environmental footprint associated with lengthy operations requiring heavy equipment and machinery for road users and surrounding areas.
- 2) Use of renewable technologies (electric power vehicles) in substitute to heavy emission trucks used for inspection activities.

- 3) Reduction of road diversions needs of heavy equipment and their environmental footprint through less equipment usage and automated solutions improving inspection efficiency and reducing revisiting needs.
- 4) More sustainable road network through optimization of GHG emissions throughout the road life cycle assisting containing the impact of climate change.
- 5) Safer road networks via precise measurements leading to better integration of inspection into maintenance planning.
- 6) Less traffic disturbance and CO₂ decrease via the automation of inspection activities in large tunnels.
- 7) Changes due to settlement are considered in this approach as reflected in actual deformation of the tunnel intrados.
- 8) The suggested approach could replace the conventional tunnel inspection and inform tunnel owners on damage/deformation escalation to consider events' escalations in routine inspection and maintenance planning
- 9) **Other deformations due to e.g. earthquakes, blasts, and other extreme events are considered in this approach as affecting the tunnel stability and shape.**

3.2. Work novelty

The solution novelty, in mind of the final and validated product will rely on: i) high accuracy measurements, ii) quicker tunnel modelling, iii) no human presence required, iv) automated modelling and aggregation, v) application ease even in long tunnels (>3km) and vi) automated 3D model comparison and defect escalation reporting. This is expected to pave a new wave of automated tunnel inspection and high-accuracy 3D modelling, maximizing value for transport infrastructure inspections linked with damage analysis, awareness, escalation and maintenance planning.

3.3. Upcoming work

During the framework of the PILOTING project activities, and based on the above first validation results, the following steps and upcoming work are planned, in view of the 2nd and 3rd methodology validation at the Egnatia Motorway infrastructure.

- 1) Integration on autonomous vehicle:
It is foreseen, that the laser scanning sensor will be positioned on an autonomous navigating vehicle that is able to autonomously position itself and the laser scanning sensor at the appropriate positions in the tunnel. Based on advanced odometry and tagging systems, the positioning accuracy of the sensor will be accurate to centimeter level.
- 2) Improvement of scan time:
Following the scanning approach validation, the scanning resolution will be adjusted to reduce the scanning time (lower inspection time, increased personnel safety) without affecting the resolution accuracy required by the inspection personnel and highway operators.
- 3) Registration and mapping of inspection points for revisiting:
To enable efficient revisiting of the exact same location/section of tunnel, we foresee the usage of odometry so that automated co-registration of models into one single model can be achieved.
- 4) Approach for comparison of models:
An automated approach is currently ongoing to develop automated mechanisms for co-registering and comparing the inspected sections. This is of particularly high value for the inspection personnel as it will enable them to calculate tunnel deteriorations over time and identify event escalations.
- 5) Computer vision to detect surface anomalies (defects):

Investigation of the quality and layout of the visual representation of the tunnel is being investigated for the capability to perform visual detection of defects (cracks, water leakages, corrosion, delamination, spalling, etc.) on the same model.

6) Final testing and validation:

The system is foreseen to undergo two upcoming rounds of validation until the end of 2022, first to study and adapt the 3D scanning methodology and second to validate the integrated sensor on the robotic vehicle.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This publication has been made following recent research results in the 'PILOTING', EC, co-funded, research project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (No 871542-5). The authors acknowledge the research outcomes of this publication belonging to the PILOTING consortium.

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